

1 N-formylation modifies membrane damage associated to PSM α 3 2 interfacial fibrillation

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8 Abstract

9 The virulence of *Staphylococcus aureus*, a multi-drug resistant pathogen, notably depends on the
10 expression of the phenol soluble modulins α 3 (PSM α 3) peptides, able to self-assemble into amyloid-
11 like cross- α fibrils. Despite remarkable advances evidencing the crucial, yet insufficient, role of fibrils
12 in PSM α 3 cytotoxic activities towards host cells, the relationship between its molecular structures,
13 assembly propensities, and modes of action remains an open intriguing problem. In this study,
14 combining Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) imaging and infrared spectroscopy, we first demonstrated
15 *in vitro* that the charge provided by the N-terminal capping of PSM α 3 alters its interactions with model
16 membranes of controlled lipid composition, without compromising its fibrillation kinetics or
17 morphology. N-formylation eventually dictates PSM α 3 - membrane binding *via* electrostatic
18 interactions with the lipid head groups. Furthermore, PSM α 3 insertion within the lipid bilayer is
19 favoured by hydrophobic interactions with the lipid acyl chains, only in the fluid-phase of membranes,
20 and not in the gel-like ordered domains. Strikingly, our real-time AFM imaging emphasizes how
21 intermediate protofibrillar entities, formed along PSM α 3 self-assembly and promoted at the
22 membrane interface, likely disrupt membrane integrity *via* peptide accumulation, and subsequent
23 membrane thinning in a peptide concentration and lipid-dependent manner. Overall, our multiscale
24 and multimodal approach sheds new light on the key roles of N-formylation and intermediate self-
25 assembling entities, rather than mature fibrils, in dictating deleterious interactions of PSM α 3 with
26 specific membrane lipids, likely underscoring its ultimate cellular toxicity *in vivo*, and in turn *S. aureus*
27 pathogenesis.

28 **Keywords.** Phenol soluble modulin; membrane; amyloid; cytotoxicity; Atomic Force Microscopy;
29 Polarized Attenuated Total Reflectance Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (p ATR-FTIR); host-
30 pathogen interaction

32 Introduction

33 *Staphylococcus aureus* is a human commensal of the microbiota and the human epithelia, which
34 can turn into an opportunistic pathogen, eventually causing life-threatening diseases. It is also well-
35 known for its key role in nosocomial infections and its resistance to many antibiotics^{1,2}. *S. aureus*
36 virulence has been shown to critically depend on the production of a family of small peptides, the
37 phenol soluble modulins (PSMs)^{3,4}: the small positively-charged α -type PSMs (~20-25 amino acids, aa)
38 and the long negatively-charged β -type PSMs (~44 aa). PSMs share intrinsic properties, such as
39 amphipathy, α -helical content, and a propensity to aggregate⁵⁻¹⁰. All PSMs are indeed able to self-
40 assemble, from soluble α -helical monomers to intermediate oligomeric entities of diverse sizes and
41 shapes and insoluble unbranched fibrils. These fibrils are mostly characterized by a stacking of β -sheets
42 where individual β -strands run perpendicular to the fibril axis and that associate *via* an extensive

43 hydrophobic core^{11,12}. Initially, this so-called cross- β scaffold was solely associated to self-assembled
 44 proteins involved in human neurodegenerative disorders (called pathological amyloids)^{13–16}. But, the
 45 past two decades have witnessed the emergence of amyloids with beneficial and physiological roles
 46 (called functional amyloids)^{17–19}, such as PSMs allowing *S. aureus* to circumvent *in fine* the immune
 47 defenses. Markedly, among all PSMs, only PSM α 3 participates in all infection processes, from cytolytic
 48 activities, to the structuration and dissemination of biofilms, and the eventual triggering of the pro-
 49 inflammation cascade³. This intriguing multi-functionality might be associated to the unique and
 50 remarkable cross- α structure, where α -helices “replace” β -strands, adopted by PSM α 3 fibrils^{5,6} or their
 51 cross- α / β polymorphism later revealed^{20,21}.

52 Among other functions, PSM α 3 exhibits, at micromolar concentrations, the highest toxicity of all
 53 PSMs towards eukaryotic cells^{5,22–24}. Such cytotoxicity primarily depends on the dynamic interactions
 54 between PSM α 3 and host cell membranes, their first targets *in vivo*. Although the exact modes of
 55 action are still unknown, PSM α 3 toxicity is not mediated by specific cell receptors but putatively
 56 requires the cross- α fibrillation of the wild-type (WT) peptides: the positive charges carried by WT-
 57 PSM α 3 (overall charge +2; Fig. 1A) likely mediate their interactions with cell membranes and fibrillation
 58 regulates the availability of such charges to subsequently drive cytotoxicity²². Based on Förster
 59 resonance energy transfer and fluorescence anisotropy experiments, Malishev *et al.* also highlighted
 60 that WT-PSM α 3 fibrils could insert into eukaryotic mimetic membranes mainly composed of
 61 zwitterionic lipids, while they could only accumulate at the negatively-charged bacterial membrane
 62 interface²⁵. Further complexifying a comprehensive picture of PSM α 3 cytotoxicity is the co-existence
 63 *in vivo* of two forms, a formylated (f-) and deformylated (df-) form, as PSM α 3 initially translates with
 64 a formyl group at the N-terminal that can be cleaved under specific conditions²⁶. This formyl group not
 65 only lowers the overall charge of the peptide (+1) but modifies the N-terminal charge of the
 66 methionine, from (-C α -NH-COH) upon translation to (-C α -NH $_3^+$) when cleaved. While the importance
 67 of terminal capping in amyloid fibril formation, structure and morphology is known^{27,28}, and partially
 68 characterized for PSM α 3²⁹ (as summarized in Table 1), the role of N-formylation in PSMs functions still
 69 remains under debate. This role has been essentially discussed in light of its pro-inflammation^{30–32} and
 70 biofilm scaffolding activities³³. Besides, *in vitro* investigation on PSM α 3 toxic activities, possibly related
 71 to its fibrillation propensity, have been only performed on the deformylated forms²⁵.

72 **Table 1. Overview of the current knowledge on the formylated (f-) and deformylated (df-) forms of PSM α 3 peptides (WT &**
 73 **F3A), in terms of fibrillation propensity and toxicity towards human and bacterial cells. Different levels of activity are**
 74 **reported: “+++”: high, “++”: moderate, “+”: low and “-”: none. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane and BM: bacterial mimetic**
 75 **membrane. Of note, fibrillation propensity of the peptides is essentially based on ThT experiments (and TEM observations),**
 76 **except when probed via AFM on supported lipid bilayers, as for df-WT and df-F3A (#). For f-WT on [EM& BM], fibrillation was**
 77 **probed while incubating lipid vesicles with an excess of peptides.**

N-ter	Peptide	<i>In vitro</i> fibrillation			<i>In vivo</i> toxicity	
		Alone	On [EM]	On [BM]	Eukaryotic cells	Gram+ Bacterial cells
f-	WT	+++ ⁷	++ ^{29*}	++ ^{29*}	+++ ³⁴	- ³⁴
	F3A				+ ³⁴	+ ³⁴
df-	WT	+++ ^{5,22,42}	+++ ^{25#}	+++ ^{25#}	+++ ^{5,22}	- ²⁵
	F3A	- ^{5,22}	- ^{25#}	++ ^{25#}	+ ^{5,22}	+++ ²⁵

78

79 The key roles of both PSM α 3 intrinsic properties and cell membrane composition in the possible
 80 toxic mechanism(s) of PSM α 3 have been further evidenced by the behaviour of a mutant peptide
 81 where the phenylalanine in position 3 has been replaced by an alanine (F3A, Fig. 1A). Indeed, these
 82 F3A-PSM α 3 peptides, that are intrinsically unable to form amyloid fibrils, induce a much reduced

83 toxicity towards human cells^{5,22} (Table 1), supporting the importance of cross- α fibrillation in the
84 deleterious activity of PSM α 3. Unexpectedly, they also lead to bactericidal activities towards some
85 gram-positive bacteria^{6,34-36}, a gained function compared to WT-PSM α 3, highlighting the species-
86 specific toxicity of PSM α 3. An *in vitro* study additionally showed that df-F3A-PSM α 3 could actually
87 aggregate on bacterial mimetic membranes, only as small oligomers deposited at the interface²⁵.
88 Consequently, the reduced cytotoxicity of F3A-PSM α 3 and its antibacterial activity could not be
89 correlated to any fibril insertion within the cell membranes, suggesting that monomers and/or
90 oligomers, independently of amyloid fibrillation, could also trigger membrane destabilization, in a lipid-
91 dependent manner. Interestingly, for pathological amyloids (e.g. A β), the amyloid cascade hypothesis,
92 according to which insoluble fibrils cause cell toxicity³⁷, is increasingly challenged as intermediate
93 oligomeric entities, formed during the self-assembly process, were reported to drive cell membrane
94 disruption, and subsequent cell dysfunction and pathogenesis³⁸⁻⁴⁰.

95 Over the last decade, an increasing knowledge about the structure and cytotoxic activities of PSM α 3
96 has been gained, especially since the discovery of its unique cross- α fibril structure. However, due to
97 the lack of integrative highly resolved techniques, amyloid(-like) fibrillation and toxicity were only
98 considered independently, without direct correlation between the morphological and structural states
99 of PSM α 3 and their biological functions *in fine*. Thus, because of the high dynamics at play both at the
100 cell membrane interface and in between entities co-existing in solution (exchange between mono-,
101 oligomers and fibrils), it still remains elusive which, and how, entities formed along PSM α 3 self-
102 assembly mediate interactions with cells. Moreover, the role of N-formylation in the possible
103 deleterious activities of PSM α 3, and the underlying molecular mechanisms, have not been addressed
104 so far. Here, we present an *in vitro* molecular investigation of the interactions between PSM α 3, in their
105 formylated form (both f-WT and f-F3A), and supported lipid bilayers (SLB) of controlled lipid
106 composition. These biomimetic systems allow (i) to overcome the high complexity of living cells, in
107 physiologically-relevant conditions⁴¹ and (ii) to disentangle how the physico-chemical properties of
108 both interacting partners lead to specific modes of action of PSM α 3. Combining highly-resolved
109 imaging and spectroscopic techniques, namely atomic force microscopy (AFM) and Attenuated Total
110 Reflectance Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR), morphological, mechanical, and
111 structural features of the peptide-membrane interactions have been revealed from the micro- to the
112 nanoscale, in real-time. Our results first indicate that N-formylation impacts the self-assembly
113 propensity of PSM α 3 at the membrane interface, in a lipid-dependent manner. Strikingly, they further
114 demonstrate that oligomeric entities are likely the membrane-active entities that tend to insert only
115 in the fluid phase of complex membranes, eventually disrupting their integrity and underscoring the
116 species-specific toxicity of PSM α 3. Such mechanistic insights into the molecular mechanisms
117 developed by the secreted PSM α 3 toxin are key in the efficient drug development strategies that
118 currently focus on targeting virulence determinants of *S. aureus* to elicit less resistance than traditional
119 antibiotics.

120

121 Results

122 **Fibrillation of formylated PSM α 3.** The self-aggregation of f-PSM α 3 was first followed by ThT
123 fluorescence, a widely used technique to monitor amyloid fibrillation *via* the increase in fluorescence,
124 ThT only binding to hydrophobic cavities within amyloid(-like) structures^{43,44}. As illustrated by the
125 typical sigmoidal curve, f-WT self-assembles into amyloid structures at 37°C, and at a concentration of
126 50 μ M in 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer complemented with 150mM NaCl (pH 8.0) (Fig. 1B). This
127 self-assembly rapidly occurs with a very short lag phase (<1h) followed by a sharp transition to the final

128 plateau reached within two hours. This kinetics does not critically depend on the peptide concentration
 129 (Fig. S1). Amyloid structures formed by f-WT after 3 days at 37°C were characterized by Transmission
 130 Electron Microscopy (TEM) as thick fibrils, often twisted and clustered into bundles, and co-existing
 131 with more globular aggregates (Fig. 1C, Fig. S2). These results are consistent with the intrinsic
 132 propensity of PSM α 3, either formylated or deformylated, to form amyloid fibrils as previously
 133 reported^{5,29}. We additionally performed such characterization for the single-point mutant F3A. f-F3A,
 134 showed no ThT binding (Fig. 1B), and remained as small aggregates even after 3 days at 37°C (Fig. 1D,
 135 Fig. S2), suggesting that f-F3A, like df-F3A, cannot assemble into amyloid structures⁵. Together, these
 136 results demonstrate that the N-terminal formylation does not change the intrinsic capacity of WT-
 137 PSM α 3 to fibrillate or the incapacity of F3A-PSM α 3 to self-assemble. For WT-PSM α 3, formylation has
 138 also no impact on the kinetics of fibrillation or the morphology of the formed fibrils (see Fig. S3 for a
 139 comparison between f- and df-WT). Of note, df-WT displays a higher ThT fluorescence intensity than
 140 f-WT, suggesting that both forms could differ either in their intrinsic amyloid structures or quantity of
 141 formed fibrils.

142 **Formylated PSM α 3 accumulates on and eventually disrupts membranes.** In light of its
 143 potential cytotoxic activities previously reported in the literature, we then wondered how f-WT
 144 behaves in the presence of the first cellular barriers, namely the cellular membranes. To reflect those
 145 peptide-membrane interactions, we investigated *in vitro* the structural and potential deleterious effect
 146 of f-WT when interacting with SLB of controlled composition. While zwitterionic lipids are used in
 147 combination with sphingomyelin (SM) and cholesterol (Chol) to mimic eukaryotic membranes (EM:
 148 DOPC/SM/Chol (67:8:25)⁴⁵), negatively charged lipids are used to reflect bacterial membranes (BM:
 149 DOPE/DOPG (1:1)⁴⁶) (Table 2). Peptides were incubated 3 days at 37°C to reach amyloid fibrillation, as
 150 determined above, and the final solution was injected on those SLBs.

151 *Table 2. Summary of the lipid compositions used in this study to investigate supported lipid bilayer (SLB).*

Controls	DOPC
	DOPC/DPPC (1:1)
Eukaryotic membrane [EM]	DOPC/SM/Chol (67:8:25)
Bacterial membrane [BM]	DOPE/DOPG (1:1)

152
 153 Polarized ATR-FTIR first allowed to assess both the organization of the lipid membrane and the
 154 structural evolution of the peptides^{47,48} following a 3h incubation of 10 μ M f-WT at the membrane
 155 interface. The membrane organization can be determined *via* the analysis of the antisymmetric and
 156 symmetric stretching modes of CH₂ of the lipid tails (ν_s (CH₂) \sim 2855 cm⁻¹ and ν_{as} (CH₂) \sim 2925 cm⁻¹) (Fig.
 157 2A). While the wavenumbers of these modes notably illustrate the fluidic properties of the membrane,
 158 the absolute absorbance at a specific wavenumber (*e.g.* ν_{as}) reflects the amount of lipids deposited on
 159 the sensor and allows to validate the formation of a single lipid bilayer (SLB). Importantly, to rule out
 160 the eventuality of membrane intrinsic instabilities over the duration of peptide treatment, spectra of
 161 pure SLB have been recorded over 3 h, and the lipid coverage reproducibly determined after 3 h (Fig.
 162 2B) is thereafter compared to the one following peptide addition. Comparisons of spectra acquired
 163 before and after f-WT addition revealed that f-WT could induce membrane damage, lipid depletion
 164 events being evaluated as a decrease in the lipid coverage of the sensor (Fig. 2A). While f-WT did not
 165 alter the lipid coverage of eukaryotic mimetic membranes (DOPC/SM/Chol), it induced a slight
 166 depletion of pure DOPC membranes (from 93 \pm 1 to 77 \pm 9 % coverage) (Fig. 2B). This could suggest
 167 that the peptides mainly impact the fluid phase of the membrane or, alternatively, that the more rigid
 168 / ordered phase (here enriched in cholesterol) could protect the membrane from f-WT deleterious

169 activity. To validate this hypothesis, we performed an additional control with a binary mixture of DOPC
 170 and DPPC, DPPC providing a rigid and more ordered scaffold for the membrane, as revealed by the
 171 lower wavenumber of the ν_{as} (CH₂) mode with the increasing concentration of DPPC (Table 1, Fig. S4).
 172 Similarly to eukaryotic membranes, lipid depletion was not observed after f-WT addition (Fig. 2B), even
 173 when varying the concentration of DPPC from 25 % to 75 % (Fig. 2B, Fig. S4). This reinforces the idea
 174 of a membrane fluidity-dependent action of f-WT peptides. Concerning the bacterial mimetic models
 175 (DOPE/DOPG), damage of the membrane was observed following f-WT incubation (decrease from 95
 176 \pm 9 to 68 \pm 25 % in lipid coverage). Given the known cytotoxic activity of PSM α 3, at micromolar
 177 concentrations and in their deformylated forms, one would expect similar functions for the formylated
 178 form herein studied and, thus, stronger impact of f-WT on SLB reflecting the composition of cellular
 179 membranes encountered *in vivo*. Such discrepancies could be explained by a dose-and time-dependent
 180 effect of PSM α 3, both parameters differing when investigating *in vivo* and *in vitro* processes. Indeed,
 181 and consistent with toxicity assays on living cells and *in vitro* leakage of vesicles containing zwitterionic
 182 lipids (with varying concentration of cholesterol)^{49,50}, we found that an increased concentration of f-
 183 WT peptides (50 μ M) caused a drastic disruption of DOPC-containing membranes after a 1h-incubation
 184 (Fig. S5). Unexpectedly though, at this high concentration, f-WT also strongly disrupts bacterial
 185 membranes, in disagreement with the absence of antibacterial activity of the deformylated form of
 186 PSM α 3.

187 To examine the role of fibrillation in such impacts on membranes, we performed the same
 188 experiments with the mutant f-F3A, also incubated for 3 days at 37°C. Similar observations were made
 189 with those peptides injected at 10 μ M. They hardly affected the DOPC-containing membranes but
 190 induced a critical depletion in the bacterial ones (from 95 \pm 9 to 35 \pm 13 % coverage) (Fig. 2B). At higher
 191 concentration (50 μ M), despite a decrease in SLB coverage, f-F3A did not significantly disrupt
 192 eukaryotic membranes or the biphasic DOPC/DPPC models, thus opposed to f-WT behaviour and
 193 consistent with the much-reduced cytotoxic activity of F3A compared to WT (Fig. S5). Besides, f-F3A
 194 induced a strong perturbation of bacterial membranes both at low (10 μ M) and high concentration (50
 195 μ M), in agreement with its antibacterial activity. Noteworthy, when the membranes were still
 196 significantly constituted (lipid coverage > 25%), thus mostly after a peptide treatment at 10 μ M, and
 197 whatever their lipid composition, both f-WT and f-F3A did not overall change the configuration, nor
 198 the mobility and packing of the acyl chains, as revealed by identical wavenumbers of ν_{as} (CH₂) before
 199 and after peptide addition (Table 3). Despite some slight, yet not significant, changes in the dichroic
 200 ratio of ν_{as} (CH₂) (Table 3), both peptides thus seem to preserve the initial organization and fluidity of
 201 the membranes, provided their deleterious impact is not drastic as observed at an elevated
 202 concentration of 50 μ M.

203 **Table 3. PSM α 3 barely compromise membrane organization and fluidity.** Wavenumber and dichroic ratio of the CH₂
 204 groups of different SLB, before (-) and after (+) peptide incubation. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane; BM: bacterial
 205 mimetic membrane.

		Peptides	f-WT		f-F3A	
			ν_{as} (CH ₂) (cm ⁻¹)	R _{ATR} (ν_{as} (CH ₂))	ν_{as} (CH ₂) (cm ⁻¹)	R _{ATR} (ν_{as} (CH ₂))
	DOPC	-	2925	1.26 \pm 0.06	2924	1.21 \pm 0.07
		+	2924	1.28 \pm 0.16	2925	1.25 \pm 0.31
	DOPC/DPPC (1:1)	-	2920	1.20 \pm 0.08	2921	1.22 \pm 0.09
		+	2921	1.36 \pm 0.15	2920	1.33 \pm 0.26
[EM]	DOPC/SM/Chol (67:8:25)	-	2925	1.27 \pm 0.07	2924	1.22 \pm 0.10
		+	2925	1.28 \pm 0.04	2925	1.23 \pm 0.09
[BM]	DOPE/DOPG (1:1)	-	2924	1.23 \pm 0.06	2925	1.34 \pm 0.14
		+	2924	1.11 \pm 0.17	2925	1.40 \pm 0.48

207 Interestingly, along with the above-mentioned effects of peptides on the membrane structure,
208 polarized ATR-FTIR revealed that both f-WT and f-F3A specifically bind and accumulate at the
209 membrane interface, as shown by the presence of Amide I and Amide II bands after a 3h-incubation at
210 10 μ M (Fig. 2A, Fig. S6). Of note, on most of the spectra recorded on the different lipid membranes
211 after f-WT incubation, those two characteristic bands were observed, with significant intensities for
212 the Amide II band, illustrating the actual strong deposition of the f-WT peptides (Fig. S6). In the case
213 of f-F3A, while those intensities were as intense as for f-WT when Amide I and II bands were observed,
214 those bands were not observed in all spectra, suggesting that f-F3A were not accumulating in all the
215 replicates (Fig. S6). Though not quantified *via* ATR-FTIR, such an observation might suggest a higher
216 avidity of f-WT for the membranes, whatever their lipid composition, as compared to its mutant f-F3A
217 but similar affinities of both peptides for the lipids. When the amide I band ($1600\text{-}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$) is
218 significantly present, its analysis allowed to assess the secondary structure element content of the
219 peptides bound to the membrane (Fig. 2C-E). Comparing spectra obtained in a lipid-free environment
220 and those acquired at the SLB interface revealed that the Amide I band shape did change, thus
221 highlighting rearrangements of the peptide structure when interacting with lipids (Fig. 2D-E).
222 Consistent with the literature on WT-PSM α 3, monomeric f-WT intrinsically adopts a α -helical
223 conformation (45 %), with additional significant contributions of turns (27 %) and random coil
224 structures (15 %), as well as a minor proportion of parallel β -sheets (13 %) (Fig. 2D). When bound to
225 DOPC- containing membranes, the α -helical content tends to be significantly promoted (above 53 %)
226 and the proportion of random coil significantly reduced (below 11 %), pointing to a structuration of
227 the peptides at the lipid interface (Fig. 2D). For instance, after interacting with eukaryotic membranes
228 (DOPC/SM/Chol), f-WT displays 58 % of α -helical content, 23 % of turns, 7 % of random coil structures,
229 and 12 % parallel β -sheets. This structuration into α -helical structures is less pronounced when
230 interacting with negatively charged bacterial mimetic (DOPE/DOPG) membranes: f-WT exhibits 51 %
231 of α -helical content, 26 % of turns, 16 % of random coil structures and 7 % parallel β -sheets. These
232 results might suggest a conformational reorganization of the f-WT peptides depending on the
233 charge surface of the membranes. As the mutant f-F3A is concerned, it mainly adopts an α -helical
234 conformation (43 %), with contributions of turns, random coil structures, and parallel β -sheets with
235 similar probabilities as f-WT (Fig. 2E). Structuration of f-F3A at the membrane interface, in a lipid-
236 dependent manner, is not as significant as for f-WT: while DOPC/DPPC and eukaryotic mimetic
237 (DOPC/SM/Chol) membranes seem to slightly favour α -helical and turn structures, the structural
238 content of f-F3A on other SLBs seems overall unchanged.

239 **Formylated PSM α 3 fibrillation is favoured by DOPC.** To understand the peptide-membrane
240 interactions, and go beyond the average information obtained by polarized ATR-FTIR on the SLB at the
241 global scale, we performed AFM high-resolution imaging experiments. Scanning SLB in real-time after
242 peptide injection allowed to simultaneously probe potential peptide aggregation and membrane
243 reorganization, at the nanoscale, in physiological conditions (*e.g.*^{51,52}). To that end, provided the SLB
244 was stable, *i.e.* its morphology did not change over time, the peptides were injected at a final
245 concentration of 5 μ M, slightly reduced compared to ATR-FTIR experiments for technical reasons.

246 The ternary DOPC/SM/Chol mixture formed a uniform and homogeneous bilayer on the mica
247 surface, with a consistent thickness of 4-5 nm, as revealed by the presence of defects in the SLB (Fig.
248 3A). Following f-WT addition, the membrane morphology remains unchanged for 30-45 minutes (Fig.
249 3A,i), a period that can slightly change depending on the experiments. After this lag time, deposition
250 and accumulation of peptides at the membrane interface are observed, as well as in the mica defects
251 (if existing), mainly as globular aggregates or short fibrils from 1 to 5 nm thick (Fig. 3A,ii - yellow arrows)

252 With time, these structures grow and elongate as thin and long fibrils from 5 to 10 nm thick (Fig. 3A,iii
253 - blue and green arrows) until the scanned region is mostly / fully covered (Fig. 3A,iv). This 3 steps
254 process was reproducibly observed on different samples and does not result from tip scanning
255 artefacts, as different areas featured the same final morphology, even if they were not scanned in real
256 time (Fig. S7). Similar observations were made on pure DOPC membranes. However, the phenomenon
257 never occurred on DOPE/DOPG membranes: similar morphology (topography and roughness) of the
258 SLB was observed in time, even after a 3h incubation with f-WT (Fig. 3B). These data first suggest that,
259 at the local scale, f-WT interacts preferentially with DOPC-containing membranes, notably eukaryotic
260 mimetic ones, rather than negatively charged bacterial membranes on which peptide deposition has
261 never been observed (Fig. 3C). Markedly, the initial deposition on the SLB only featured small
262 aggregates and/or short fibrils, able to subsequently elongate, and substantially differing from the
263 thick clustered fibrils observed by TEM (Fig. 1B). This observation unambiguously reveals the co-
264 existence of both mature and thick fibrils and oligomeric, if not monomeric, entities within the f-WT
265 solution, despite the 3 days incubation at 37°C which allowed to reach saturation of amyloid formation
266 (as shown by ThT fluorescence, Fig. 1). Moreover, these oligomeric entities appeared as nucleation
267 spots on the SLB for the propagation of thin and elongated fibrils, suggesting the ability of zwitterionic
268 DOPC to promote amyloid fibrillation, at solid interfaces (Fig. 3C). Interestingly, controls on
269 DOPC/DPPC bilayers highlighted the presence of fibrils only in the liquid phase of DOPC (Fig. 3A). The
270 gel-phase domains of DPPC, ~ 0.5 - 1 nm thicker than the surrounding DOPC phase (*e.g.* see Fig. S9),
271 remained intact upon interactions with f-WT. The real-time imaging showed that f-WT deposition and
272 aggregation actually occurs within – and is restricted to – the DOPC phase, the growing fibrils even
273 adopting the shape of the DPPC domain edges (Fig. 3A,iv). These nanoscale observations confirm the
274 affinity of f-WT for DOPC-containing SLB and the role of membrane fluidity in eventually dictating
275 peptide-membrane interactions (Fig. 3C), consistently with our ATR-FTIR data. They additionally
276 highlight that (i) the compact and ordered organization of DPPC prevents the f-WT accumulation, and
277 (ii) the hydrophobic edges between gel-like DPPC domains and fluid DOPC phase potentially drive
278 fibrils elongation and shape. They finally provide a direct visualization of the timely evolution of
279 peptide morphology, not accessible by other techniques at this resolution: f-WT peptides evolve from
280 small aggregates initially bound to the SLB to long and thin fibrils covering the membrane. This
281 morphological transition reinforces the structural rearrangements determined *via* ATR-FTIR.

282 **Oligomeric entities of PSM α 3 eventually insert and disrupt membranes.** While those AFM
283 observations emphasized the lipid-dependent fibrillation of f-WT, they also highlighted a reciprocal
284 impact of the peptide on the SLB. Mostly on the eukaryotic and biphasic DOPC/DPPC bilayers, local
285 damages were regularly observed as a membrane thinning, if not lipid depletion (Fig. 4). Upon peptide
286 binding and fibrillation, an area thinner than the fluid phase (~ 0.5 - 1 nm) was observed around the
287 elongating fibril, and both this area and the fibril are concomitantly growing (Fig. 4A, Fig. S8). This
288 specific area was also revealed by the nanomechanical imaging evidencing different DMT modulus: it
289 appears softer than the lipid membrane, and barely stiffer than the fibril itself (Fig. 4A). While in some
290 cases, those areas were smooth and homogeneous, suggesting a membrane thinning effect or a partial
291 lipid depletion induced by the peptide (Fig. 4A), in other samples they seemed to be filled with peptidic
292 material (Fig. 5). Indeed, part of the area could either appear “fuzzy” with small aggregates or covered
293 with thin filaments protruding from 0.5 to 2 nm above the SLB (Fig. 5A-B, yellow arrows), thus much
294 thinner than the mature fibrils (~ 5 nm in height) also observed in the same areas (Fig. 5A-B, blue
295 arrows). As for mature fibrils, these filaments, thereafter named protofibrils, grow in time and
296 altogether form a soft area (Fig. 5C). In this area, in between fibrils and/or protofibrils, a decrease in
297 height of approximately 0.5 - 1 nm was observed compared to the surrounding lipid membrane, and
298 less frequently holes of ~ 2 nm deep (Fig. 5A). When the area is densely populated with protofibrils,

299 resulting in a typical wavy pattern, those variations were less pronounced (Fig. 5B-C). These variations
300 in the SLB thickness might be due to the insertion of the f-WT peptides within the membrane, as also
301 supported by the ATR-FTIR data, locally disturbing its organization and eventually leading to the
302 disruption of the outer monolayer of the SLB. Such membrane damage following f-WT action is further
303 supported by the disruption of SLB incubated with a more concentrated f-WT solution ($> 15 \mu\text{M}$) (Fig.
304 S9). In the same way as at low concentration, short fibrils first deposit, and subsequently grow in/on
305 the liquid phase of the SLB, locally disrupting the membrane as revealed by a 2 nm thinning. Then,
306 these thinner areas progress and change the shape of the 0.5-1nm thicker DPPC domains, until they
307 totally disappear, suggesting that both liquid and gel-like phases of the membrane are depleted by f-
308 WT at elevated concentration, which is consistent with the significant decrease in lipid coverage
309 measured by ATR-FTIR.

310 Importantly, the presence of small aggregates and protofibrils, still able to grow and elongate in
311 time at the interface of - and even within - the liquid phase of the DOPC membranes, suggests the co-
312 existence of oligomers and mature fibrils within the f-WT solution incubated for 3 days at 37°C . It also
313 emphasizes that those oligomeric entities might be the membrane-active ones, as they tend to
314 precede the mature fibrils of $> 5 \text{ nm}$ thickness. To validate this hypothesis, we performed the same
315 real-time experiments, on SLB of diverse controlled composition, after injecting a solution of f-F3A
316 peptides preincubated 3 days at 37°C . Unexpectedly, this mutant, unable to intrinsically form amyloid
317 fibrils (Fig. 1), behaved very similarly as f-WT peptides: it was able to accumulate and elongate as fibrils
318 on eukaryotic mimetic membranes (DOPC/SM/Chol), and more largely on DOPC-containing
319 membranes tested in this study, whereas no deposition or fibrillation was observed on bacterial
320 mimetic membranes (DOPE/DOPG) (Fig. 6A, Fig. S10). Besides, like f-WT, f-F3A preferentially interacts
321 with - and self-aggregates in - the fluid phases of the SLB, as shown by the clustering of elongating
322 fibrils only in DOPC, excluded from the DPPC domains (Fig. 6B, Fig. S10). The transition from small
323 aggregates to thin protofibrils and mature fibrils was finally observed over time, with the former
324 propagating as a soft front potentially inserted within the membrane, and eventually locally disrupting
325 the membrane integrity (Fig. 6B). These nanoscale observations highlight the role of SLB, containing
326 DOPC, as a potential inducer of the aggregation of f-F3A that is otherwise unable to self-assemble in a
327 lipid-free environment. Thus, this mutant cannot serve as a control for the role of intermediate
328 amyloidogenic entities in the potential damage induced by f-WT PSM α 3 on SLB.

329 Alternatively, to investigate this point, we carried out experiments where f-WT peptides were
330 injected on the DOPC/DPPC SLB as a monomeric solution (Fig. 7). Instead of pre-incubating the
331 peptides for 3 days at 37°C to favour amyloid fibrillation, and work with this final solution, the f-WT
332 solution has been frozen once prepared to start the experiment only with monomeric entities (f-
333 WT_m). Although the timescale cannot be quantitatively compared, as mentioned above it can differ
334 substantially between different samples, the 3 steps process, observed after injecting f-WT on the
335 DOPC-membranes, also occurred upon addition of f-WT_m, with similar durations. After a lag-time
336 (Fig. 7A,i), small aggregates ($< 2 \text{ nm}$) first appeared (Fig. 7A,ii – yellow arrows), from which fibrils (~ 5
337 nm) start to elongate in time (Fig. 7A,iii and Fig. 7B), before covering the whole membrane (Fig. 7A,iv).
338 Accumulation of f-WT_m was not observed on DOPE/DOPG membranes (data not shown). The
339 aggregates either form small domains, softer than the surrounding membrane and stiffer than the
340 thick fibrils (Fig. 7B), or assemble into thin protofibrils eventually inserted into the membrane, as
341 revealed by holes around them (Fig. 7C). The accumulation of f-WT_m at the interface of DOPC-
342 membranes is further supported by the presence of the Amide I band in ATR-FTIR spectra acquired
343 after a 3 h incubation of f-WT_m on SLB (Fig. 7D). Such infrared experiments also confirm similar impact
344 of the f-WT solutions at $10 \mu\text{M}$, either after fibrillation or frozen at the initial monomeric state, on the
345 integrity of SLBs with various controlled composition (Fig. 7E). However, increasing the concentration

346 to 50 μM lead to substantial differences between fibrillated and initial monomeric solution of f-WT
347 (Fig. S11). While both solutions significantly disrupt all membranes, whatever their lipid composition,
348 the deleterious activity of f-WT_m is much reduced on DOPC and DOPE/DOPG membranes compared
349 to f-WT. When SLB are enriched in lipids favouring the formation of gel-like domains (either DPPC or
350 cholesterol), f-WT and f-WT_m similarly and drastically destroy the SLBs. This tend to highlight that (i)
351 entities present over the first 1h (here, the time of SLB treatment by f-WT_m) probably also exist in
352 the final f-WT fibrillated solution (after 3 days at 37°C) and (ii) these entities likely mediate the
353 membrane-deleterious activity of f-PSM α 3. Alternatively, one could argue that distinct entities present
354 in f-WT and f-WT_m (e.g. oligomers vs. fibrils) could lead to similar damage on SLB but the real-time
355 AFM observations are not in favour of such hypothesis, as similar morphological evolution of peptides
356 aggregates and protofibrils are observed for both f-WT and f-WT_m. Overall, our AFM and ATR-FTIR
357 results point to a predominant role of f-WT oligomeric, if not monomeric, entities in interacting with
358 supported bilayers, and their preferential aggregation into the liquid phase of these membranes, with
359 the gel-like domains, if present, remaining intact.

360

361 Discussion

362 Combining spectroscopic and high-resolution imaging approaches *in vitro*, we have shown, that both
363 f-WT and f-F3A behave very similarly at the interface of DOPC-containing membranes and bacterial
364 (DOPE/DOPG) membranes. For the former membranes, at low concentration (5-10 μM), both peptides
365 first tend to deposit and accumulate on the membrane as revealed by ATR-FTIR spectroscopy (Fig. 2)
366 and visually confirmed by AFM imaging (Fig. 3, 6). Subsequently, fibrils were observed to grow in time
367 until they eventually form large “carpets” of thin and long fibrils, only in the fluid phase of the
368 membrane. Concomitantly, membrane disruption was locally probed as a thinning effect co-localizing
369 with the growing peptides (Fig. 4, 5). Those local perturbations are consistent with the minor impact
370 of f-WT and f-F3A on DOPC-containing SLB, in terms of lipid depletion (Fig. 2). Significantly, those
371 deleterious effects on membrane integrity are favoured at higher concentration of f-WT (25-50 μM) as
372 illustrated by a decrease in lipid coverage (Fig. S5) and progressive disappearance of the membrane
373 (Fig. S9) following peptide treatment.

374 **Role of N-formylation in dictating PSM α 3-membrane interactions.** We have shown that the
375 deposition and fibrillation propensities of formylated (f-) PSM α 3 on SLB substantially differ from those
376 of deformylated (df-) PSM α 3 previously reported²⁵. On one hand, while df-WT forms elongated fibrils
377 at the interface of both eukaryotic (DOPC/SM/Chol) and bacterial (DOPE/DOPG) membranes, f-WT
378 only accumulates and self-aggregates on the former ones. Noteworthy, f-WT and df-WT exhibit similar
379 morphology when elongating on membranes, with a thickness and width of 5 to 10 nm for the thinnest
380 fibrils. On the other hand, while df-F3A forms small aggregates only on bacterial membranes
381 (DOPE/DOPG), f-F3A displays the exact same behaviour as f-WT with a DOPC-induced fibrillation, and
382 an absence of deposition on DOPE/DOPG. Such differences underscore the role of N-formylation in the
383 mechanism of action of PSM α 3 at the cell membrane interface and could arise, in a simplistic view,
384 from the different charges carried by the peptides at the N-terminal when formylated ($-\text{C}_\alpha\text{-NH-COH}$)
385 or not ($-\text{C}_\alpha\text{-NH}_3^+$). Indeed, while electrostatic interactions are favoured between deformylated
386 peptides and negatively charged DOPE/DOPG membranes, they are reduced with the formylated
387 peptides, which might explain the absence of both f-WT and f-F3A accumulation on bacterial
388 membranes (AFM imaging, Fig. 3, 6). Similarly, this reduced charge at the N-terminal would decrease
389 the repulsions between formylated peptides and phosphatidylcholine (PC) groups. While this
390 reasoning can explain the interactions between f-F3A, unlike df-F3A, and DOPC-containing

391 membranes, it cannot account for the similar behaviour of df-WT and f-WT as they both fibrillate on
392 DOPC. This behaviour points to an additional critical role of the phenylalanine in position 3, previously
393 reported in light of PSM α 3 toxicity^{5,34}, as this aromatic residue would favour the interactions with PC,
394 unlike the alanine present in the F3A mutant. Overall, the different behaviour of f- and df- PSM α 3, and
395 WT and F3A, at membrane interfaces, demonstrate that surface induced aggregation of PSM α 3 is
396 driven by hydrophobic as well as electrostatic interactions with the lipid acyl chains and their head
397 group, respectively. This lipid-dependent fibrillation is actually shared with pathological amyloids, with
398 kinetic effects (either catalysing or slowing down the aggregation) that relate to the net charge of both
399 lipids and proteins⁵³. Such surface-triggered aggregation is also in line with the versatile adsorption
400 and amyloid formation on both hydrophilic and hydrophobic surfaces of PSM α 1-4⁵⁴, as well as other
401 bacterial functional amyloids, such as curli proteins CsgA and CsgB of *E. coli*⁵⁵.

402 **Mechanism of action of PSM α 3 at the membrane interface.** The “carpet” behaviour that we
403 observe with both f-WT and f-F3A at specific SLB interfaces is usually preceded by local membrane
404 disruption, the extent of which depends on peptide concentration, as above-mentioned, and lipid
405 composition. Indeed, experiments on the binary DOPC/DPPC SLB, that exhibits a clear phase
406 separation between liquid-like DOPC domains and gel-like DPPC domains, have allowed to reveal that
407 both PSM α 3 fibrillation and membrane perturbation occur only in the liquid phase of the SLB.
408 Increasing peptide concentration ultimately leads to disruption of both domains. Such phenomena
409 further evidence the role of both electrostatic and hydrophobic interactions for PSM α 3 to exert its
410 potential membrane damage. While the ordered state of DPPC acyl chains would prevent insertion of
411 PSM α 3, the mismatch between fluid DOPC and gel-like DPPC domains would enhance the hydrophobic
412 interactions with the peptides, thus favouring the nucleation of fibril insertion and elongation within
413 the fluid phase of the membrane from the DPPC edges. Such fluidity-dependent fibrillation and toxicity
414 of amyloids have been previously reported for pathological amyloids. For instance, while fluid POPC or
415 liquid-expanded DPPC (at $T > T_m$) facilitates fibrillation of A β by favouring a high mobility of the
416 peptides, the liquid-condensed phase of DPPC can retard their self-aggregation⁵⁶, fibrils can even be
417 excluded from such domains in lipid monolayers⁵⁷. Besides, in these fluid membranes, our results point
418 to a membrane perturbation, either as thinning or formation of holes, induced by PSM α 3 once a
419 threshold concentration of peptides is reached. This is highly reminiscent of the carpet-like model by
420 which other amphipathic α -helical peptides, the antimicrobial peptides (AMP), permeate cellular
421 membranes⁵⁸: they first bind to the membrane, cover it and, above a critical density, conformational
422 rearrangement of the peptides within the membrane leads to micelle formation, until the eventual
423 total membrane disruption. Our AFM data further indicate that peptides, notably the thin protofibrils,
424 propagate as a “front” and might be embedded in the membrane, probably in the upper leaflet from
425 the topographical protrusions observed. These observations are partially in agreement with the
426 insertion of df-WT PSM α 3 fibrils, but not df-F3A, within the hydrophobic core of DOPC/SM/Chol
427 bilayers²⁵. This might also suggest a mode of action for f-PSM α 3 that implies transmembrane pore
428 formation, where the peptides could insert perpendicularly in the lipid bilayer. As our ATR-FTIR data
429 do not support a change in membrane fluidity and organization, such pores would result from a barrel-
430 stave pore model, where the amphipathic structure of PSM α 3 favours interactions between its
431 hydrophobic residues and the lipid acyl chains and preserve the hydrophilic lipid head group
432 arrangement⁵⁹. Such a mix between a carpet-like and a pore formation models has been described for
433 some AMP that, after accumulating at a critical concentration on bacterial membranes, disrupt their
434 integrity by two-dimensional lateral diffusion within the membrane, illustrated *via* AFM imaging by
435 holes spanning the full or partial (the outer leaflet) bilayer or only a thinning effect⁶⁰⁻⁶².

436 **Role of oligomeric entities in membrane perturbation.** Markedly, our AFM data further revealed
437 that membrane thinning, and possible disruption, were usually associated to growing protofibrils that

438 precede the occurrence of mature thick fibrils. Moreover, those phenomena occurred when the
439 peptides (f-WT or f-F3A) were injected either as a monomeric solution (Fig. 7) or after a 3 days-
440 incubation at 37°C to promote amyloid fibrillation (Fig. 4-6). This result first suggests that a reservoir
441 of mono-, more probably oligomeric entities (such as protofibrils) co-exists with the fibrillar entities at
442 the end of the self-assembly process. Besides, these oligomers are likely the membrane-active entities,
443 leading the potential deleterious activities, and eventually the ultimate cytotoxicity. This hypothesis is
444 in agreement with recent evidence, based on mutation assays yielding non-fibrillating peptides or on
445 different levels of cell toxicity among PSMs, that cross- α fibrillation is not sufficient to account for
446 PSM α 3 lytic activities^{6,22}. Xuan *et al.* also demonstrated, by salt-inducing different PSM α 3 assemblies,
447 that oligomers / curvilinear fibrils, and to a lesser extent rigid fibrils, rather than amorphous
448 aggregates, exert high cytotoxicity towards HEK cells *in vivo*⁶³. Our *in vitro* observations also highlight
449 that a dynamic exchange between oligomers and fibrils entities, and mutual interactions / aggregation
450 with cell membranes, are required to explain the deleterious activities of both f-WT and f-F3A, in partial
451 agreement with the *in vivo* and *in vitro* behaviour of deformed PSM α 3^{22,25,42}. They further revealed,
452 at the nanoscale, that membrane disruption (either thinning or holes that partially span the
453 membrane) is usually locally associated to the presence of oligomers or protofibrils. Interestingly,
454 soluble oligomers of different pathological amyloid proteins were also earlier reported to cause
455 membrane disruption, unlike fibrils, *via* different modes of action: while some exert a detergent-like
456 effect⁶⁴, other induce a membrane thinning due to an increase in conductance without pore
457 formation⁶⁵. Those results thus fuel the debate on the increasingly challenged amyloid cascade
458 hypothesis⁴⁰, according to which insoluble fibrils of pathological amyloids cause cell toxicity³⁷.

459 Despite our above hypothesis and interpretation, it still remains enigmatic why low concentrations of
460 f-WT and f-F3A induced similar effects at the membrane interface, given the reduced toxicity of the
461 deformed forms of the mutant peptides *in vivo*. To nuance this paradox, one should take into
462 account several points. (1) Despite high cytotoxicity of WT at elevated concentration, not specific to
463 any cell, compared to F3A, both peptides actually exhibit similar lytic activities against HEK cells at
464 concentration lower than 3.5 μ M⁵, suggesting that below a critical concentration both peptides could
465 act similarly. (2) Though simplified membrane models are key in understanding fundamental molecular
466 mechanisms *in vitro*, *in vivo* processes are much more complex with cellular membranes displaying
467 high heterogeneity in the lipid composition, and embedding proteins that could interfere with the lipid
468 pathway. For instance, PSMs are known to bind the formyl peptide receptors 2 (FPR2) on the
469 membrane of immune cells, their complex triggering a host immune cascade^{30,32}, and an increased
470 phagocytosis of *S. aureus*⁶⁶. However, PSMs cytotoxicity could be enhanced from the intracellular
471 environment after phagocytosis²³, thus potentially making interactions of PSMs with such membrane
472 proteins an indirect contribution to the lytic functions of PSMs.

473

474 Conclusions

475 In conclusion, this work aimed at providing mechanistic and molecular insights into the cytotoxicity of
476 PSM α 3, functional amyloids secreted by *S. aureus* pathogens, by investigating their interactions with
477 model biomimetic membranes. Indeed, while the remarkable cross- α fibrillation of PSM α 3 has been
478 correlated to its toxicity towards human cells *in vivo*, the molecular mechanisms underlying such
479 function have so far remained elusive. Especially, the dynamic and mutual interactions at play between
480 PSM α 3 self-assembling entities and cell membranes have been so far partially ignored. Here,
481 combining spectroscopic and highly-resolved imaging techniques, we have bridged the behaviour of
482 PSM α 3 at the whole membrane level to its local impact on the lipid membrane organization, in real-

483 time and at the nanoscale. Markedly, we have demonstrated *in vitro* the key roles of N-terminal
484 formylation and intermediate oligomeric entities in driving membrane damages, likely reflecting
485 PSM α 3 lytic activities *in vivo*. Specifically, we have shown that N-formylation, the physiological capping
486 of PSM α 3 when initially secreted by *S. aureus*, can modify the peptide binding to cell membranes. It
487 does so, in a lipid-dependent manner, by modulating electrostatic interactions with the lipid head
488 charges. In addition, we have revealed that zwitterionic lipids promote the fibrillation of PSM α 3 at the
489 membrane interface, only in fluid phases of the bilayer - thus excluded from the ordered and compact
490 domains. Hydrophobic interactions between the peptides and the lipid acyl chains thus likely dictate
491 the potential accumulation and insertion of PSM α 3 in the lipid bilayer. Finally, we have evidenced that
492 oligomeric and protofibrillar structures, rather than mature fibrils, are likely responsible for membrane
493 disruption, *via* membrane thinning and eventual pore formation following peptide accumulation in a
494 “carpet” fashion. Such findings, beyond highlighting the critical importance of PSM α 3 N-formylation,
495 thus additionally fuel the increasing debate on the amyloid cascade hypothesis, even in the context of
496 functional amyloids.

497

498 **Materials and methods**

499 **Materials.** Formylated PSM α 3 peptides, in the WT (f-MEFVAKLFKFFKDLLGKFLGNN) and mutant F3A
500 (f-MEAVAKLFKFFKDLLGKFLGNN) forms, were purchased from GenScript at ≥ 98 % purity. Mass
501 spectrometry experiments were performed to confirm the purity of the peptides. DOPC, DPPC, DOPE,
502 DOPG, cholesterol (Chol, ovine wool, > 98 %), and sphingomyelin (SM, brain porcine) were purchased
503 from Avanti Polar Lipids, trifluoroacetic acid (TFA, ≥ 99 % HPLC grade) from Fisher Scientific and
504 thioflavin T (ThT) and hexafluoroisopropanol (HFIP) from Sigma Aldrich.

505 **Peptide preparation.** f-WT and f-F3A solutions were prepared by dissolving the peptide powder at a
506 concentration of 1 mM in a (1:1) mixture of HFIP/TFA, for 1 h at room temperature (RT). Solvent was
507 evaporated under a stream of dry N₂ and solvent residues were evaporated under vacuum in a
508 dessicator for 2 h. The resulting peptide film was rehydrated with ultrapure water at a concentration
509 of 1 mM, on ice, and sonicated for 5 min. This solution was then further diluted, at the desired
510 concentration, in a 10 mM sodium phosphate buffer complemented with 150 mM NaCl (pH 8.0). It was
511 finally centrifuged (10 000 rpm, 5 min, 4°C), and the supernatant was collected to avoid initial
512 aggregates. This final peptide solution was either fast-frozen in liquid nitrogen, and kept at -80°C for
513 investigation on monomeric peptide solution, or incubated for 3 days at 37°C under gentle agitation
514 (~400 rpm).

515 **Thioflavin T (ThT) fluorescence assay.** The kinetics of PSM α 3 self-aggregation was monitored using
516 the variations of the fluorescence intensity of ThT dye ($\lambda_{\text{excitation}} = 449$ nm / $\lambda_{\text{emission}} = 482$ nm).
517 Fluorescence measurements were performed on a CLARIOstar plus (BMG Labtech) plate reader, using
518 standard 96 or 384 well flat-bottom black plates, sealed with a transparent cover sticker to avoid
519 evaporation. Assays were performed 3 times independently, each in triplicate, in a final volume of 200
520 or 50 μ L, for 96 and 384 well plates respectively, containing (i) 200 μ M ThT and appropriate volumes
521 of (ii) buffer (10 mM sodium phosphate buffer complemented with 150 mM NaCl (pH 8.0)) and (iii)
522 peptides to reach the desired concentration (from 10 to 100 μ M). The peptides were freshly prepared
523 as described above, prior to ThT fluorescence assays, to avoid aggregation preceding the first
524 measurements. The ThT solution was obtained by diluting a stock of ThT at 10 mM in water into the
525 appropriate buffer at a final concentration of 1 mM. The fluorescence intensity was measured at 37°C,
526 with a 500 rpm orbital shaking for 15 s before each cycle, with up to 1000 cycles of 5 min each.

527 **Transmission electron microscopy (TEM).** TEM was performed on peptide solutions after 3 days
528 of incubation at 37°C (following either ThT fluorescence assays or incubation “on bench” under similar
529 conditions), to assess the formation of aggregates and amyloid fibrils for each peptide solution
530 prepared. 4.2 µL of the peptide solution (50-100 µM) were adsorbed onto glow-discharged carbon
531 coated 300 mesh copper grids for 2 min and the excess solution was blotted with filter paper. Negative
532 staining was then performed using a 1% uranyl acetate solution applied to the grids for 30 s and blotted
533 again for the grids to dry. The grids were finally examined using a CM120 electron microscope
534 operating at 120 kV with an LaB6 filament. Different areas of the grids were imaged to get a
535 representative picture of the entities (f-WT and f-F3A) formed over the incubation.

536 **Supported lipid bilayer (SLB) preparation.** Phospholipid vesicles were prepared as followed. DOPC,
537 DPPC, DOPG, DOPE, SM, and Chol dissolved in chloroform were pipetted into an Eppendorf in
538 appropriate volumes to reach a molar ratio of (67:8:25) for DOPC/SM/Chol, (1:1) for DOPE/DOPG and
539 (1:1) for DOPC/DPPC and stirred to get homogeneous solutions. The solvent was then removed first by
540 evaporation under a stream of dry N₂ and then by placing the ependorf under vacuum in a desiccator
541 for 2 h. The lipid films were then rehydrated with the same buffer as the one used for peptide
542 preparations (10 mM sodium phosphate buffer complemented with 150 mM NaCl (pH 8.0)) to form
543 multilamellar vesicles (MLV) at a final concentration of 2 mg/mL. This MLV suspension was then
544 sonicated over 3 cycles of 10 min., with an amplitude of 40 % and 3 s pulses to obtain small unilamellar
545 vesicles (SUV). While sonicating, the ependorf was kept in an ice bath to limit heating. The SUV
546 suspension was finally filtered on 0.2 µm filters to remove eventual residues from the ultrasound
547 probe, and stored at 4°C, before any experiment, for maximum 2 weeks.

548 From those SUV suspensions, SLB were formed on the appropriate substrate according to the vesicle
549 fusion method. For AFM experiments, 100 µL of a 1 mg/mL SUV suspension were applied for 30 min.
550 on a freshly cleaved mica disk, heated to 60°C if needed (*e.g.* for the binary mixture DOPC/DPPC).
551 Attention was paid to avoid dewetting: buffer was added regularly for the SLB to always stay hydrated.
552 In case of heating, the sample was slowly cooled down to RT for 30 min. Whatever the temperature of
553 incubation, the samples were finally heavily and carefully rinsed with the buffer (~ 10 times, V = 100µL)
554 to remove all unabsorbed vesicles. 80µL of buffer were finally added onto the SLB for AFM
555 investigation in liquid. For ATR-FTIR experiments, 20 µL of a 1 mg/mL SUV suspension were applied
556 directly on an ATR germanium crystal hosted in a homemade liquid chamber. After 5 min., the SLB was
557 rinsed 6 times with buffer, letting a final volume of 20 µL for infrared spectra acquisition. For both AFM
558 and ATR-FTIR experiments, when working with anionic lipids (*e.g.* DOPG), 1-2 mM of CaCl₂ was added
559 to the buffer to favour SUV fusion on the substrates.

560 **Attenuated total reflectance Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR).** ATR-FTIR
561 spectra were recorded, in buffer conditions (V = 20 µL) at room temperature (20 °C), on a Nicolet iS50
562 FTIR spectrometer equipped with an MCT detector cooled with liquid N₂, and an ATR accessory
563 mounted with a germanium crystal (one reflection). Polarized spectra (incident light at 0° and 90°, *i.e.*
564 *s*- and *p*-polarizations respectively) were recorded with 200 scans and a spectral resolution of 2 cm⁻¹.
565 To remove the contribution of ambient air and buffer, background and buffer spectra were first
566 collected for both *s*- and *p*-polarizations, and then subtracted from all samples spectra either during
567 acquisition or in post-processing. SLB was then formed on the germanium crystal, and rinsed as
568 described above. Spectra in *s*- and *p*-polarizations were collected before peptide addition, or after 3 h
569 to assess its stability over time. Provided the correct formation and stability of the SLB, the peptide of
570 interest was then injected in the final volume of 20 µL at a final concentration of 50 or 10 µM for 1 or
571 3 h respectively. Spectra following peptide-membrane interactions were collected after rinsing the
572 liquid chamber, to avoid the contributions of non-adsorbed peptides and lipids in solution close to the
573 germanium crystal. ATR-FTIR spectra were post-processed using the Omnic software, to subtract the

574 buffer contribution and correct the baseline at the following points: 3500, 3000, 2800, 1800, and 1000
575 cm⁻¹. Deconvolution of the Amide I band was performed with OriginPro (OriginLab). Every experiment
576 was performed at least 3 independent times. For clarity, only spectra obtained in the *p*-polarization
577 (and resulting analysis) are presented herein, as the same variations following peptide-membrane
578 interactions were observed in the *s*-polarization and the *p-pol* spectra were the most intense.

579 **Atomic force microscopy (AFM).** AFM imaging of the SLBs was performed using the PeakForce
580 Quantitative Nano-Mechanics (PF-QNM) mode on an Dimension Fast-Scan setup (Bruker) in buffer
581 conditions at room temperature (20 °C). Nitride-coated silicon cantilevers (SNL-C, Bruker) with a
582 nominal spring constant of 0.24 N/m, and a tip radius of 2 nm, were used and calibrated before any
583 experiment using the thermal noise method. The images, analysed and processed with the Nanoscope
584 Analysis software (Bruker), were acquired with a scan rate of ~1 Hz, a Peakforce amplitude of 50 nm
585 and a Peakforce frequency of 1 kHz, and the applied force kept as low as possible to minimize any tip-
586 induced damage (< 1 nN). Once the formation and stability of the SLB have been confirmed by AFM
587 imaging, the peptides of interest were injected at a final concentration of 5 μM, in a total volume of
588 80 μL, if not otherwise stated. The same area (typically 3x 3 μm²) was then imaged in real time with
589 an approx. 1 image every 5 min. to probe and correlate eventual peptide aggregation and membrane
590 damage. Zoom out and different areas were also scanned to ensure that those phenomena are not
591 zone-dependent, or due to tip scanning artefacts. Of note, along with the topographic images, AFM
592 forces curves were recorded in each pixel of the scanned area, and mechanical images of the areas
593 were simultaneously recorded. In this study, we present the Derjaguin, Muller, Toropov (DMT)
594 modulus map of the areas of interest. This DMT modulus (*E*) is obtained by fitting the retract curve
595 with the following model:

$$596 \quad F_{tip} = \frac{4}{3}E\sqrt{Rd^3} + F_{adh}$$

597 Where F_{tip} is the force on the tip, F_{adh} the adhesion force if existent, *R* the tip radius, and *d* the tip-
598 sample distance.

599 Every experiment was performed at least 3 independent times, and the images presented herein are
600 representative of the obtained results.

601

602 **Author contributions.** LB, KJ and MMG collected and analysed all experimental data (ThT, TEM, ATR-
603 FTIR and AFM). AV and MMG supervised and trained students in AFM investigation. MMG conceived
604 the project for which she obtained national and European funding. LK, SL, CF, MM and MMG designed
605 the experimental methodology, and interpreted experimental results. All authors contributed to the
606 manuscript writing.

607 **Conflicts of interest.** There are no conflicts to declare

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A f-WT f-MEFVAKLFFKFFKDLLGKFLGNN
 f-F3A f-MEAVAKLFFKFFKDLLGKFLGNN

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750 **Figure 1. Fibrillation of formylated PSM α 3.** (A) Amino-acid sequences of the wild type (WT) and single-
 751 point mutation (F3A) PSM α 3, with a formylation (f-) at their N-terminal. (B) Kinetics of PSM α 3 fibril
 752 formation followed by ThT fluorescence, at 37°C and a peptide concentration of 50 μ M. Error bars
 753 stand for the standard deviation between three replicates. (C-D) Negatively stained TEM images of
 754 PSM α 3 (C, f-WT and D, f-F3A) after 3 days of incubation at 37°C. Yellow and green arrows point at
 755 mature fibrils and aggregates respectively.

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758 **Figure 2. Membrane disruption via f-PSM α 3 accumulation. (A)** ATR-FTIR spectra of a DOPC/SM/Chol
 759 SLB before and after a 3 h incubation with f-WT at 10 μM , focused on the CH_2 lipid and Amide bands.
 760 **(B)** Lipid coverage of the ATR-FTIR sensor, determined via the variations in $v_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ intensity, for SLB
 761 of diverse composition following PSM α 3 addition (3 h, 10 μM). Results are presented as mean \pm
 762 standard deviation of at least three independent replicates. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$. EM: eukaryotic
 763 mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic membrane. **(C)** Deconvolution of the ATR-FTIR spectra for
 764 the Amide range of a DOPC SLB after a 3 h incubation with f-WT at 10 μM . **(D-E)** Secondary structure
 765 content derived from the ATR-FTIR spectra of (D) f-WT and (E) f-F3A after interacting with different
 766 SLB for 3 h at 10 μM . All spectra presented, and the resulting analysis, were obtained in the p -
 767 polarization.

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770 **Figure 3. Fibrillation of f-WT PSMα3 on DOPC-containing membranes. (A-B)** AFM topography images,
 771 at representative timepoints, of various SLB interacting with 5 μM f-WT. After a lag-time during which
 772 the SLB remains intact (i), small aggregates (ii -yellow arrows) first appear before elongating as thin (iii
 773 - blue arrows), and sometimes stacked (green arrows), fibrils in the fluid DOPC phases, eventually
 774 covering the whole membrane (iv). Color scale bar: 20 nm for DOPC-SLB, 10 nm for the other SLBs. EM:
 775 eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic membrane. **(C)** Schematic representation of the
 776 lipid-dependent affinity, and possible fibrillation, of f-WT at the membrane interface.

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779 **Figure 4. Membrane disruption by f-WT PSM α 3 fibrils.** Topographical and mechanical analysis of the
 780 DOPC/DPPC membrane, as an f-WT fibril elongate in time. **(A)** AFM topography and DMT modulus
 781 images, and **(B)** the corresponding height and modulus profiles, along the dashed lines, point to a
 782 membrane thinning (white arrows and grey areas) around the growing soft fibril. AFM images were
 783 obtained after f-WT, injected at 5 μ M, starts interacting with – and accumulating – at the SLB interface.
 784 Color scale bars: 10 nm for the topography images and 2 log (Pa) for the DMT modulus images.

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788 **Figure 5. Insertion of f-WT PSM α 3 protofibrils in the membrane.** Topographical analysis of **(A)**
 789 DOPC/DPPC and **(B)** DOPC/SM/Chol membranes, at a representative timepoint when f-WT (injected at
 790 5 μ M) co-exist as protofibrils (yellow arrows) and mature fibrils (blue arrows). Height profiles along the
 791 dashed lines in the AFM topography images show both entities (corresponding colored areas), as well
 792 as holes and/or membrane thinning (grey areas). **(C)** Elongation of f-WT protofibrils, as a thin and soft
 793 « front », probed by AFM topography and DMT modulus images. Color scale bar: **(A)** 10 nm, **(B-C)** 6 nm
 794 and 2 log (Pa).

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796 **Figure 6. Fibrillation of f-F3A PSM α 3 on DOPC-containing membranes. (A)** AFM topography images
 797 of eukaryotic (DOPC/SM/Chol) and bacterial (DOPE/DOPG) mimetic membranes before and after
 798 interacting with 5 μ M f-F3A. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic membrane.
 799 **(B)** Topographical analysis of a biphasic DOPC/DPPC SLB on which f-F3A has aggregated as thin
 800 protofibrils (yellow arrow) and mature fibrils (blue arrow). The height profile along the dashed line
 801 notably points to holes in the SLB (grey areas) surrounding the presence of (proto-)fibrils of f-F3A. Color
 802 scale bar: 10 nm.

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805 **Figure 7. f-WT oligomers are the membrane-active entities.** (A) AFM topography images, at
 806 representative timepoints, of a DOPC/DPPC SLB interacting with a 5 μM monomeric solution of f-WT
 807 (f-WT_m). f-WT_m first accumulate as small aggregates (ii - yellow arrows) and fibrillate (iii - blue
 808 arrows) only in the fluid DOPC phase, until the eventual full membrane coverage (iv). (B) DMT modulus
 809 image of f-WT_m at the DOPC/DPPC interface, after 60 min of incubation. The height and modulus
 810 profiles, along the dashed line, are presented that correlate the presence of a small aggregate and a
 811 fibril with the softest areas. (C) The thin protofibrils and fibrils eventually co-localize with thinner areas
 812 of the membrane (grey areas in the profile). Color scale bars: 20 nm in (A,C), 1,7 log(Pa) in (B). (D) ATR-
 813 FTIR spectra (*p-pol*) of a DOPC/SM/Chol SLB before and after a 3 h incubation with f-WT_m at 10 μM,
 814 focused on the CH₂ lipid and Amide bands. (E) Comparison of the lipid coverage, obtained in *p-pol*,
 815 of the ATR-FTIR sensor for SLB of diverse composition following a 3 h incubation with 10 μM fibrillated (f-
 816 WT) and monomeric (f-WT_m) f-WT solutions. Results are presented as mean ± standard deviation of
 817 at least three independent replicates. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic
 818 membrane.

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823 **Figure S1.** Kinetics of **(A)** f-WT and **(B)** f-F3A fibrillation followed by ThT fluorescence, at 37°C and
 824 varying peptide concentrations. Error bars stand for the standard deviation between three replicates.

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829 **Figure S2.** Negatively stained TEM images of **(A-B)** f-WT and **(C)** f-F3A peptides obtained after 3 days
 830 incubation at 37°C. **(A)** f-WT and **(C)** f-F3A were deposited per se, in buffer conditions. **(B)** f-WT were
 831 centrifuged, and the pellet resuspended in ultrapure water, to properly image the mature fibrils only.
 832 Two types of areas were observed, with f-WT fibrils highly clustered into large bundles (top) or small
 833 clusters with even isolated fibrils (bottom).

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837 **Figure S3. (A)** Comparison of the fibril formation of formylated (f-) and deformed (df-) PSM α 3
 838 followed by ThT fluorescence (37°C, peptide concentration 50 μ M). Error bars stand for the standard
 839 deviation between three replicates. **(B)** Negatively stained TEM images of df-WT fibrils obtained after
 840 3 days incubation at 37°C.

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844 **Figure S4. (A)** Lipid coverage of the ATR-FTIR sensor, determined *via* the variations in $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ intensity,
 845 for binary DOPC/DPPC SLB, with varying concentration of DPPC, and following f-WT addition (3 h, 10
 846 μ M). Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation of at least three independent replicates. **(B)**
 847 Table of the wavenumber and dichroic ratio of the CH_2 of DOPC/DPPC membranes with varying ratio
 848 of DPPC, before (-) and after (+) f-WT addition at 10 μ M for 3h. Analyzed spectra were obtained in the
 849 p - polarization.

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852 **Figure S5.** Lipid coverage of the ATR-FTIR sensor, determined *via* the variations in ν_{as} (CH_2) intensity,
 853 for SLB of diverse composition following PSM α 3 incubation for 1 h at 50 μM . Results are presented as
 854 mean \pm standard deviation of at least three independent replicates. *** $p < 0.001$. Analyzed spectra
 855 were obtained in the p - polarization. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic
 856 membrane.

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859 **Figure S6. Quantification of PSMα3 deposition at the SLB interface.** (A) ATR-FTIR spectra (*p-pol*) of a
 860 DOPC/DPPC SLB before and after a 3 h incubation with f-F3A at 10 μM, illustrating the accumulation
 861 of the peptides at the membrane interface (Amide I and II observable). (B) Absolute intensities, in the
 862 *p-pol*, of the Amide II band (~ 1550 cm⁻¹) after a 3h incubation of PSMα3 (f-WT and f-F3A) on SLB of
 863 different compositions. (C) Deposition occurrence of PSMα3, estimated by the ratio between the
 864 number of spectra featuring the Amide I and II bands and the total number of spectra recorded. EM:
 865 eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic membrane.

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868 **Figure S7.** Fibrillation of f-PSM α 3 (WT and F3A) at the membrane interface (here, exemplified with
 869 DOPC/DPPC (1:1)) is independent of the AFM-tip scanning. Similar fibrils were always observed in areas
 870 different from those scanned in real-time. Color scale bars: 15nm.

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874 **Figure S8.** Topographical analysis of a DOPC/SM/Chol membrane interacting with f-WT (5 μ M). The
 875 AFM topography image and the corresponding height profile along the dashed line showcase short
 876 fibrils (\sim 5 nm) surrounded by areas thinner than the SLB (white arrows and grey area). Small holes can
 877 also be observed in the membrane, independently of the f-WT presence. Color scale bar: 10 nm.

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880 **Figure S9.** Topographical analysis of a DOPC/DPPC membrane interacting with f-WT at a concentration
 881 of 15 μ M, at representative timepoints. Height profiles along the dashed lines in the AFM topography
 882 images are shown to quantitatively measure membrane damage and peptide aggregation. Red circles
 883 point to areas where membrane thinning starts occurring (from 1 to 2 nm), as also shown by the height
 884 profiles over time.

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887 **Figure S10. Fibrillation of f-F3A PSM α 3 on DOPC-containing membranes. (A)** AFM topography images,
 888 at representative timepoints, of various DOPC-containing SLB interacting with 5 μ M f-F3A. After a lag-
 889 time during which the SLB remains intact (i), small aggregates (ii - yellow arrows) first appear before
 890 elongating as thin fibrils (iii - blue arrows), covering a larger and larger proportion of the membrane
 891 (iv). EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane. **(B)** Timelapse of the growth of both protofibrils (yellow
 892 arrows) and mature fibrils (blue arrows) of f-F3A in the fluid DOPC phase of a binary DOPC/DPPC SLB.
 893 The front of protofibrils is further evidenced by their mechanical properties (DMT modulus image at
 894 45min of incubation), softer than the surrounding membrane. Color scale bars: 10nm, 2 log(Pa).

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898 **Figure S11.** Lipid coverage of the ATR-FTIR sensor, determined *via* the variations in $\nu_{as}(\text{CH}_2)$ intensity,
 899 for SLB of diverse composition following f-WT incubation at 50 μM for 1 h, injected as a fibrillated
 900 solution (3 days at 37°C, f-WT) or an initial monomeric solution (f-WT_m). Results are presented as
 901 mean \pm standard deviation of at least three independent replicates. Analyzed spectra were obtained
 902 in the p - polarization. EM: eukaryotic mimetic membrane, BM: bacterial mimetic membrane.

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